

DEVELOPING OF COMPOSITE CNG PRESSURE VESSELS

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SUMMARY : Development of composite CNG (compressed natural gas) pressure vessel with three-piece HDPE (High Density Polyethylene) liner and metal end nozzles was studied. The CNG environmental tests carried out for HDPE, resins and reinforcing fibers showed no significant damages. The metal end nozzle was designed to minimize the gas leak which was verified by FEM analysis. Most ideal fiber tension was obtained by experimental method and fiber volume fraction, V_f , obtained by image analyzer were 55.4% in hoop and 55.6% in helical directions, respectively. During the cure, the vessel was rotated to allow uniform resin content and when a constant internal pressure of 0.62 bar is applied, the vessels burst at 28% higher pressure and had smoother surfaces. The burst tests for under-wound and fully wounded vessel showed satisfactory results.

KEYWORDS : compressed natural gas, high density polyethylene, FEM analysis, fiber volume fraction, internal pressure

INTRODUCTION

The amount of gasoline is limited on earth and, moreover, the gasoline using vehicles pollute the air and are becoming a serious problem throughout the world. Along with solar or electric powered vehicles, the natural gas vehicles are one of the pollution-free vehicle being developed. Compressed Natural Gas pressure vessel made of Carbon/Epoxy Composite with polyethylene liner weighs about 60% less than that of Aluminum. For passenger vehicles, composite CNG pressure vessels provide much safer burst behavior as compared to that of metallic CNG. The purpose of the present study is to develop composite CNG pressure vessels for mid-size passenger vehicles. Operating and burst pressure of the vessel required are 25 and 56 bar, respectively. The liner used for CNG pressure vessels is made of HDPE and high strength carbon fibers are used for filament winding of the vessels. At each end of the vessel, the designed "Metal End Nozzle" is inserted for simpler manufacturing as well as easier injection of the natural gas.

TEST OF MATERIALS IN CNG ENVIRONMENT

In order to find out the effect of CNG environment, fibers(carbon, glass and kevlar), resins and polyethylenes have been put into a chamber with CNG environment at room temperature. The specimens were placed in a test chamber up to 1 year. To provide CNG environment, an

internal pressure of 35 bar was maintained with natural gas in the chamber. Each specimen was tensile tested before being placed into a test chamber. The specimen's tensile strength has been tested periodically during one year. Pure fibers have been tensile tested according to ASTM D3379. For all specimens, a loss of their tensile strength has been hardly observed(Fig. 1). The materials tested are vinylester (National), epoxy (Ciba-Geigy), carbon fiber (high strength, Taekwang Ind. Ltd.), fiber glass (Hankuk Fiber Glass Co.), Kevlar 49 (Dupont), HDPE1 (Honam Petroleum Ind.) and HDPE2 (SamSung Chemical Co.). All these specimens were placed in a chamber with CNG environment and tested periodically during one year.

Fig. 1 : Specimens' tensile strength vs time in CNG environment (HDPE1 : Honam Petroleum Ind., HDPE2 : SamSung Chemical Co.)

DESIGN OF METAL END NOZZLE

The effective manufacturing of HDPE liner depends on the design of metal end nozzle. The design also can help to prevent gas leaks which may occur by a possible separation of metal and HDPE due to the repetitive change of internal pressure. For this reason, a metal end

nozzle has been designed and its schematic drawings are shown in Fig. 2 and 3, respectively. The thick line represents the attached area between HDPE and metal. The circled area details a notch. HDPE is filled into this notch when liner is manufactured and paste is added onto this area. When the pressure vessel is being used, internal pressure provides pressure to the paste and HDPE toward the metal which provides better sealing and seems to prevent gas leak more effectively. Moreover, in order to prevent HDPE and metal separation due to twisting of the vessel, a 3 mm x 7.5 mm x 15mm hole is carved out symmetrically at the base of the metal end nozzle(Fig. 4).

Fig. 2 : Schematic drawing of CNG vessel

Fig. 3 : Schematic drawing of a Metal End Nozzle

Fig. 4: Schematic drawing of symmetric holes at 3mm depths (crosshatched)

The validity of the design has been examined by NISA FEM software package. The element used for the analysis are NISA NKTP #3, axisymmetric 2D and the boundary condition was $D_{x,y,z} = 0$. Input materials properties : for metal, $E_x = 200$ Gpa, $\nu = 0.3$ and for HDPE, $E_x = 3.4$ Gpa, $\nu = 0.35$. As for load, only internal pressure of 0.62 bar was applied. One half of the nozzle shape was modeled (Fig. 5). Light colored part represent metal and dark part represent HDPE. The arrows indicate the internal pressure applied and the bunched up arrows indicate the restraints. Fig. 6 and 7 represent deformations and Von Mises stresses after the analysis.

Fig. 5 : Modeling with one half of the nozzle.

The deformed shapes in Fig. 6 shows that there are no significant separation between metal and HDPE on inner part of the nozzle. Also, the maximum stress resulted in Von Mises stress analysis is only 26.36 bar in the metal which is too low to cause any significant effect considering $E_{\text{metal}} = 20,000$ bar and $E_{\text{HDPE}} = 340$ bar. This result indicate that the gas leak may not occur.

Fig. 6 : Deformations after FEM analysis

Fig. 7 : Von Mises stresses after FEM analysis

Dome area is the area that connects Metal End Nozzle and cylinder part of the vessel. Having appropriately smooth connection, the stress concentration can be avoided and easier winding can be attained. Especially, the bending moment should not exist when the internal pressure is applied such that the composite's strength in dome and cylinder part can be utilized most efficiently when in use. This dome shape can simply be achieved from the simple geometric construction around cylinder and dome area under the condition that the bending moment is zero in dome area.

Optimal V_f by Filament Winding Process

In order to achieve optimal V_f in filament winding process, the various V_f are measured by image analyzer for varying fiber tensions with various number of composite layers in hoop direction. By examining the results in Fig. 8, V_f 's were increasing with tensions higher than 1000g and decreasing with tensions lower than 750g from which the ideal tension for present filament winding machine appears to be about 800 - 850g and, with this tension, the V_f in hoop and helical directions were measured to be 55.4% and 55.6%, respectively.

Fig. 8 : V_f vs number of layers with varying fiber tension in hoop direction

USER FRIENDLY PROGRAM

A user friendly program (KIMM - PV) has been developed to calculate most appropriate fiber directions, thickness of helical layer, thickness of hoop layer, thickness of liner, etc. This program was formulated from the laminated plate theory for cylinder and shell, respectively. The main boundary condition is the compatibility of the stresses at the boundary of cylinder and shell. This program is used to find the conditions for best structural performance for the hybrid pressure vessels. The flow chart of the program is shown in Fig. 9.

MANUFACTURING

The HDPE liner is installed in a filament winding machine. Then, the vessel is wound by use of carbon fiber strands with the specified angles and thickness. Curing is done according

to the manufacturer's recommendation. Fig. 10 represents the flow of FRP pressure vessel's manufacturing. During curing an internal pressure of 0.62 bar was applied. It prevents collapsing of HDPE during the curing process.

Fig. 9 : Flow chart of KIMM - PV

Fig. 10 : Flow of manufacturing

SPECIFICATIONS

The specifications of a CNG pressure vessel are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Specifications of a CNG pressure vessel

Type	F/W pressure Vessel with non-load sharing PE Liner	
Pressure	Operating Pressure	25 bar
	Proof Pressure	35 bar
	Burst Pressure	56 bar
Outer Diameter of the Liner	380 mm	
Length of the Liner	880 mm	
Weight	> 30 kg	
Internal Volume	80 liter	

BURST TEST

Specimens subjected to burst tests are summarized in Table 2 and their results are summarized in Table 3. In Table 2, K and R specimens are under-wounded compared to the ones that are to be burst at required 56 bar.

Table 2. Stacking sequences of the specimens

Specimen	Stacking Sequence	No of Layers
K 1	[15] ₂ , [90] ₂ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₃ , [15], [90] ₂ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₄	25 layers
K 2	[15], [90] ₂ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₂ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₃ , [15], [90], [15], [90] ₃	25 layers
R 1	[15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆	40 layers
R 2	[15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆ , [15], [90] ₆	40 layers
S 1*	[15], [90] ₄ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₆ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₄ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₆ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₄	40 layers
S 2*	[15], [90] ₄ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₆ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₄ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₆ , [15] ₂ , [90] ₄	40 layers

Table 3. Burst test results (Internal pressure of .62 bar is applied during the cure) (1 bar = 10 Mpa)*

specimen	Burst press	[15]	[90]	Tot Wt	Fiber	Epoxy	Failure Mode
K 1	20 bar	14	11	25.4kg	7.2kg	3.4kg	Cylinder
K 2	20 bar	14	11	22.5kg	6.6kg	4.9kg	Cylinder
R 1	28 bar	10	30	27.6kg	8.6kg	6.3kg	Nozzle
R 2*	36 bar	10	30	28.5kg	8.6kg	6.7kg	Nozzle
S 1*	58 bar	16	24	29.8kg	9.5kg	7.1kg	Cylinder
S 2*	59 bar	16	24	30.1kg	9.6kg	7.3kg	Cylinder

TEST SET UP

Burst test is carried out by a safe test set up shown in the schematic drawing of Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Schematic drawing of safe test set up.

RESULTS

- 1) For all fibers, resins and polyethylenes tested in a chamber of CNG environment up to 1 year showed hardly any degradations.
- 2) FEM analysis showed that the metal end nozzle seems to be an appropriate design that may help prevent gas leaks.
- 3) KIMM - PV program seems to agree with burst test results.
- 4) CNG pressure vessels cured with internal pressure of 0.62 bar burst at 28% higher pressure and resulted with smoother surface.
- 5) V_f , obtained by image analyzer, were 55.4% in hoop and 55.6% in helical directions, respectively.

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